

Buildings BIM Library Management Platform Project

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Abstract

In the ever-evolving landscape of the Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations (AECO) industry, efficient collaboration among diverse stakeholders is paramount. Building Information Modelling (BIM) has emerged as a vital tool for streamlining information exchange in this complex ecosystem. At the heart of the BIM framework lies the BIM library, a repository of standardized and data-rich BIM objects. These libraries enhance efficiency by providing reusable, standardized elements that promote collaboration and reduce redundancies. This research is dedicated to formulating guidelines for a BIM library management platform tailored to the specific needs of a large-scale design, engineering, and construction company. Its central aim is to bridge the growing gap between technical and non-technical stakeholders by democratizing data accessibility. By ensuring that crucial data is readily available and comprehensible to all, this study aims to cultivate inclusivity and collaboration. The research objectives encompass workflow analysis, identification of hindrances and inefficiencies in BIM processes, assessment of BIM object storage and retrieval, comprehensive case study investigation, and synthesis of findings to develop comprehensive guidelines for a purpose-built BIM library management platform. Key findings underscore the overreliance on technical expertise, which leads to bottlenecks for non-technical stakeholders. Insights from document analysis and user feedback highlight the imperative for optimizing

the user experience, enhancing BIM object accessibility, and facilitating real-time updates. Case study analysis further substantiates these findings by revealing key metrics for the development of a BIM library management platform. These metrics encompass User Interface, backend functionality, collaboration and interaction, user authentication and Access Control, Administration Panel, and Integration with external tools. The study recommends the implementation of these requirements along with technical documentation, ongoing monitoring, evaluation, and technical assessments for the platform development. The research also raises intriguing questions about the potential evolution of intelligent BIM objects and their incorporation into BIM libraries, opening doors for the exploration of immersive technologies like AR, VR, and XR. In sum, this study stands as a valuable reference for AECO industry organizations seeking to establish or optimize their dedicated BIM library management platforms.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/kvi-u1HHjLs>

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